

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear and then the polar bear. Discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. May be darkish or mild brown (cinnamon), typically even white. Not at all times black in coloration. 900,000 and never threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear might be discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. However, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to 6 toes in size. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, however their fur can range from darkish brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on rare events. They've pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are a few of the perfect at climbing bushes. Their comparatively smaller size and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb trees for safety, meals, and even hibernation. The vast majority of their weight loss plan is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Food regimen: Their varied food regimen offers them the power to stay in a big vary of habitats. Additionally they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Dangerous? They are the most definitely bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And sure, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Brown bears are essentially the most widespread of all bear species, found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Grizzlies are accountable for almost all bear assaults in North America, with 46 per year. Though their conservation standing is "least concern", their spread-out nature and lowered habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a large number of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large construct, a dish-formed face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the guidelines, which led to the name of probably the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt young mammals such as elk and moose. Their colour varies from light blonde to darkish brown. The 2 subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are discovered within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 toes lengthy, and have a shoulder peak of 3.3 feet. □□ Food plan: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been recognized to prey on giant mammals. Coastal grizzlies are usually larger than these discovered in the Rocky Mountains as a consequence of a richer diet. Each year there are 46 attacks and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Recognized for their aggressive habits, grizzlies are liable for probably the most bear attacks in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are solely found on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Dimension: Kodiak bears are virtually as large as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, 8 feet lengthy, and four toes tall at the shoulder. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Their weight loss plan is similar to mainland grizzly bears. Nevertheless, because of more plentiful meals sources, the islands can support a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to turn out to be their own subspecies. This has led to a extra advanced social construction which leads to less conflict between bears. □□ Harmful? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears can be aggressive. Because of their isolation, there is just one attack on humans each other yr. Largest species of bear on the planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Weight loss plan is usually made up of meat, often from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the largest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur appears white but is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears range within the snow-covered arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Dimension: Grownup polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and may be 7 to 10 toes tall. They're a threatened species because of loss of habitat from local weather change. Regardless of their enormous dimension polar bears may be fast, maintaining a 6 mph pace within the water. □□ Features: Compared to different bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Food regimen: Their food plan consists largely of animals, especially seals which they will smell from a mile away. Although they seem white, their fur is actually clear and their skin is black. □□ Harmful? Polar bears may be extremely harmful. They see people as potential prey. Assaults are uncommon due to the remote nature of their habitat. Identified for its cream colour chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Easy to tame and infrequently common in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands throughout Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account susceptible. □□ Dimension: One of many smaller species, adults weigh around 300 pounds and stand forty seven to 75 inches tall. □□ Food regimen: Depending on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects,

and honey. Attacks on people are rising as folks encroach on their habitat. ☐☐ Dangerous? They're certainly one of the best bears to tame (and therefore common in circuses), however Asian black bears are more aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found only in China. 99% of its food plan is bamboo. In actual fact, the second person in history to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas protecting his sheep. Identified for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped body. ☐☐Location: Pandas are discovered only in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 stay in the wild and they are thought of a susceptible species. ☐☐ Size: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and can be over four feet tall, a powerful feat considering they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at beginning. It also has a detailed cousin, the Qinling panda which has the same sample in light brown and white. ☐☐ Eating regimen: Unlike other bears the panda's food regimen is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. ☐☐ Options: The enormous panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped physique. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them common: they poop over 40 times a day! ☐☐ Dangerous? Assaults are rare but harmful, given that pandas have considered one of the best chew forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing 55 to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch long tongue for slurping up insects and honey. ☐☐Location: The Sun bear is discovered in the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is uncertain however thought of weak and on the decline because of lack of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for their gallbladders and different body parts utilized in conventional medicines. ☐☐ Measurement: They stand solely 39 to fifty five inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. ☐☐ Options: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a short snout. They are named for their pale, horseshoe-shaped chest patch that looks like a rising sun. In addition they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. ☐☐ Food regimen: Sun bears tear apart trees and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In actual fact, they have an incredibly lengthy tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. ☐☐ Harmful? As a result of its shy nature, assaults are uncommon. Long, shaggy fur and mane gave them the name sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. ☐☐Location: The Sloth bear is discovered within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of less than 20,000, they are thought of weak. ☐☐ Dimension: They're 55 to 75 inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. ☐☐ Features: With their lengthy shaggy fur and mane, they're simple to inform aside from different Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very fast and can out-gallop humans. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging upside down from trees. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their large curved claws. ☐☐ Eating regimen: Their weight loss plan consists of termites, ants, and fruit. ☐☐ Dangerous? They are one of the vital aggressive bears, with essentially the most attacks on humans, principally resulting from shock encounters. They blow the mud around with huge puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they are often heard 600 feet away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and do not mix nicely with rhinos and elephants, often charging at one another when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's last brief-confronted bear. The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that appear like glasses. This susceptible species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found in the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. ☐☐ Dimension: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to 79 inches [chimpanzee teddy bear](#) tall. ☐☐Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last short-confronted bear and the one bear native to South America. ☐☐ Features: The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that sometimes appear to be glasses. They spend most of their time in trees the place they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard treasured fruit and carcasses. ☐☐ Diet: Spectacled bears are mostly herbivores with a weight loss program consisting of principally cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, but they may opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. ☐☐ Dangerous? Living in distant mountains, these shy bears often is the least dangerous of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears however larger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a rare hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear behavior is nearer to the polar bear. They function the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they have been documented stomping toys, just like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably on the London Zoo in 1859, however have not been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot but DNA assessments have been unable to find out what sort of bear it was. Adorable koalas will not be bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears either, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that may survive in area. Most bear attacks happen when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Purple pandas? They're in their own household which can be nearer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR

SURROUNDINGS. Look ahead to bear scat and bear tracks that may point out a bear is nearby, wherein case you wish to be extra vigilant. Listed here are just a few tips you should use to stop bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies safe. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're right here so they don't unintentionally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you'll have great intentions, a bear is prone to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Items (AT CAMP).** When you see a bear, do not attempt to strategy or feed it. This consists of meals, but in addition your toiletries, for instance. Whichever method you select, ensure it's at the very least 200 toes away out of your tent so you do not appeal to bears to your campsite. 4. **Stay CALM.** Should you meet a bear, do not run. Attempt to make your self look as big as possible, waving your arms above your head. You can also extend a jacket above your head to make your self look bigger. Lock this stuff in a bear canister or use a bear bag to cling them up in a tree. Don't scream or attempt to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A last RESORT).** Communicate to it calmly and slowly again away. Full instruction on how to make use of bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously close (30 feet) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward. 6. **Fight Again.** If all else fails and a bear assaults you, do not play lifeless. Which bear is the largest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 ft long, and 4. Zero to 5.25 toes tall, the biggest bear by each dimension and weight is the polar bear. The largest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Battle again with all of your energy and hope that it's going to again down. Which bear is the most harmful? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is known for the most attacks. When in bear country, it's always sensible to carry bear spray. It's well deserved, especially when cubs are around. Every year there are roughly forty six grizzly assaults, 6 leading to dying. In North America, grizzly bears have probably the most fearsome popularity. Which bear is the strongest? While you're most more likely to see an American black bear, on common there is only one assault per yr. In terms of raw bite power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chunk reigns supreme. All bears are robust and not to be messed with. When utilizing the chunk force quotient (chew power relative to size), the solar bear packs the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found within the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to flee the hearth however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he grew to become an icon and to at the present time is the star of the longest-running public service announcement marketing campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear recognized for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. More importantly Yogi Bear has impressed countless thru-hikers to try to grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some traits of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a duty-free lifestyle. He also is likely to be the first bear to receive his pilot's license. Earlier than he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son often would visit on the London Zoo. Winnie is short for "Winnipeg," the town in Canada near the place he was from. Chris additionally wrote The way to Hike the Appalachian Path. Equal elements backpacking food and ultralight gear. After via-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to supply quick, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic tips, guides and the way-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

